

TOWARDS THE DEVELOPMENT OF LIFELONG LEARNING: AN ASSESSMENT OF THE COLLECTIVE LEADERSHIP PRACTICES and IMPLEMENTATION OF STUDENT SUPPORT SERVICES

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ABSTRACT

The study delved to ascertain the development of lifelong learning: an assessment of the collective leadership practices and implementation of student support services. The researcher used the descriptive correlational design to describe the data, characteristics used and the population in the study. It was conducted at the Laguna State Polytechnic University randomly selecting 792 students across four campuses. The findings are as follows: The Perceived Collective leadership practices of Student Support Services are interpreted as “Practiced”. The Perceived Implementation of Student Support Services is interpreted as “Implemented”. The Perceived Development of Lifelong Learning Competencies is interpreted as “Developed”. The correlation of Development of Lifelong learning to the Collective leadership is found “significant”. The Test of Correlation between the developed lifelong learning and the student support services are all found “significant”. The regression analyses for collective leadership and the student support services “significantly” affect the Lifelong Learning Competency. The Test of Difference on Collective leadership and Implementation of the student support services “does not differ significantly”. There is “no significant difference” on the Level of Developed Lifelong Learning Competencies. Based on the findings, the following hereby concluded: The hypothesis posited that there is no significant relationship between the developed lifelong learning and the collective leadership practices and the Implementation of student support services is rejected. The hypothesis that the level of developed lifelong learning competencies does not significantly affect the Implementation of collective leadership practices is not sustained. Thus, the researcher recommends a review on the practice of collective leadership in the Implementation of student support services. Action plans with emphasis on students lifelong learning competencies may be devised. Parallel research may be made in order to apply the collective leadership and student support services of the four campuses.

Keywords: Collective leadership; Life-long learning; Student Services;